

Jnanadeepa

Pune Journal of Religious Studies

ISSN 2249-1503

www.punejournal.in

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4284674

Stable URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4284674>

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Abstract: Sin is a term used mainly in a religious context to describe an act that violates a moral code, or the state of having committed such a violation. Commonly, the moral code of conduct is decreed by a divine entity. The root meaning of the English word sin is actually, “He is guilty as charged.” This in turn implies that the person committing the offence knew, or ought to have known, that his act would be an offence before he committed it. This word actually captures the meaning that many religious traditions ascribe to sin. Sin is often used to mean an action that is prohibited or considered wrong; in some religions (notably in some Christian sects) sin can refer to a state of mind rather than a specific action. Colloquially, any thought, word, or act considered immoral, shameful, harmful, or alienating might be termed “sinful.”

Keywords: Sin in Islam, Sinful Situation, Guilt, Shame

<p>Cite as: Lazar, G. (2008). The Meaning and Function of Sin in the Islamic World-View (Version 1.0). <i>Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies</i>, Jan-June 2008 (Vol 11/2), 40-59. http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4284674</p>

20001-07-05 | Updated on Nov 20, 2020

The Meaning and Function of Sin in the Islamic World-view

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Introduction

Sin is a term used mainly in a religious context to describe an act that violates a moral code, or the state of having committed such a violation. Commonly, the moral code of conduct is decreed by a divine entity. The root meaning of the English word *sin* is actually, “He is guilty as charged.” This in turn implies that the person committing the offence knew, or ought to have known, that his act would be an offence before he committed it. This word actually captures the meaning that many religious traditions ascribe to sin. Sin is often used to mean an action that is prohibited or considered wrong; in some religions (notably in some Christian sects) sin can refer to a state of mind rather than a specific action. Colloquially, any thought, word, or act considered immoral, shameful, harmful, or alienating might be termed “sinful”.

Buddhism does not recognise the idea behind sin because in Buddhism, instead, there is a “Cause-Effect Theory”, known as Karma, or action. In general, Buddhism, illustrates intentions as the cause of Karma, either good or bad. Furthermore, most thoughts in any being’s mind can be negative. Vipaka, the result of one’s Karma, may create low quality living, hardships, destruction and all means of disharmony in life and it may create healthy living, easiness, and harmony in life. Good deeds produce good results while bad deeds produce bad results. Karma and Vipaka are one’s action and its result. Panchasila is the fundamental code of Buddhist ethics, willingly undertaken by lay followers of Gautama Buddha. It is a basic understanding of the Noble Eightfold Path, which is a Buddhist teaching on ways to stop suffering. Sin is a concept used primarily in the Abrahamic religions, (Judaism, Christianity and Islam) describing a transgression against the will of God, which calls for repentance and at times penance. Judaism regards

the breaking of the commandments or the Jewish Law to be a sin. Judaism teaches that sin is an act, and not a state of being. Humankind was not created with an inclination to do evil, but has that inclination “from his youth” (Genesis 8:21). People do have the ability to master this inclination (Genesis 4:7) and choose good over evil (Psalm 37:27). Judaism uses the term “sin” to include violations of the Jewish law that are not necessarily a lapse in morality. According to the Jewish Encyclopedia, “Man is responsible for sin because he is endowed with free will (“*behirah*”); yet he is by nature frail, and the tendency of the mind is to evil: “For the imagination of man’s heart is evil from his youth” (Gen. VIII, 21; Yoma 20a; Sanhy. 105a). Therefore God in His mercy allowed people to repent and be forgiven”.¹ The Jews believe that all people sin at various points in their lives, and hold that the divine justice is tempered with divine mercy. According to them, a state of sin does not condemn a person to damnation; only one or two truly grievous sins lead to anything like the Christian idea of hell. Their liturgy of “the Days of Awe” states that prayer, repentance and charity are the means of atonement for sin.

As for Protestant Christians use the term ‘sin’ primarily to refer to what they see as “humanity’s inherently sinful nature”. This is while the Catholics mostly use the word for actual instances of sin, calling “the sinful nature of humans” as *concupiscence*”, in the sense of ‘an innate tendency of human beings to do evil’. Most denominations of Christianity hold the belief that the sin of Adam and Eve’s disobedience to God is passed on to their descendants and thus the whole humankind is accursed with that Original Sin, from which no salvation is possible unless one believes in the atoning death on the cross of the Son of God. The concept of sin in Islam is different from that in most, if not all other religions. According to Islam, a sin is an action which constitutes the violation of Islamic teachings. Any action or word, which runs counter to the will of Allah is a sin. In Islam, sin is simply an act, never a state of being. This essay will aim to bring out the meaning and function of sin in Islam.

Concept of Sin in Islam:

Foundational Motifs

The foundational source in the gradual codification of Islamic understanding of sin was the Muslim understanding and interpretations of the Quran and practices of Muhammad. Its meaning has always been in the context of active submission to God (Arabic: Allah), performed by the community in unison. The motif force in Islamic understanding of sin is the notion that every human being is called to “command the good and forbid the evil” in all spheres of life. Muslims understand the role of Muhammad as attempting to facilitate this submission. Another key factor in the field of Islamic understanding of sin is the belief that humankind has been granted the faculty to discern God’s will and to abide by it. This faculty most crucially involves reflecting over the meaning of existence, which, as John Kelsay in the *Encyclopedia of Ethics* phrases, “ultimately points to the reality of God”. Therefore, regardless of their environment, humans are believed to have a moral responsibility to submit to God’s will and to follow Islam (Quran 7:172). Our discussion on the understanding of sin in Islam will follow this foundational motif.

Sin and Islam

To begin with, the Islamic concept of sin is similar to the Jewish view. In fact, the religion of Islam is the natural culmination of the progressive revelation of God from the very first prophet to the last one, Prophet Muhammad. Consequently, Islam believes in all the prophets of God, from Adam to Muhammad, including Abraham, Moses and Jesus. According to the Islamic creed, the original religion taught by all these prophets was and is always Islam, which is the peaceful submission to the One and Only God. Thus, the concept of sin as taught by all the prophets of God ought to be the same. The closeness between Judaism and Islam in this regard is obvious; but in Christianity we find a great difference, which results from the influence of Saul of Tarsus, who is later known as St. Paul. He introduced into Christianity the ideas of ‘God becoming a man’ and ‘God dying for the sins of humans’. Such concepts are entirely alien to the Semitic religious tradition and considered ‘pagan’, according to the Islamic view. Islam sees sin (dhanb, thanb) as anything that goes against the will of God. Another strong

word used to denote sin is *ma'siyah* which literally means transgression or disobedience. Anything that violates the commands of Allah is transgression or sin. According to Islamic theology unbelief and polytheism are the biggest of all sins. We have the ability to abide by His will and this is the meaning of the word Islam. Still we have the ability to ignore His will or deliberately oppose it due to the fact that God has given us freedom – though within limits. Islam is our conscious and peaceful submission to the will of Allah. The purpose of our existence as human beings is to worship and serve Allah – or to fulfil His will. A solid foundation of worshipping Allah is to show gratitude to Him for the great gifts He has granted us. Following this will bring us the greatest benefits in this life and the next. It is in trying to do this that our intentions are purified and it is by our intentions that we are judged. The Quran teaches that “the human soul is certainly prone to evil, unless the Lord does bestow His Mercy” and that even the prophets do not absolve themselves of blame (Quran 12:53).

In contrast to the traditional Christian teaching that human nature is basically evil owing to Original Sin, Islam teaches that human being is essentially good. There are many elements to human nature and each one has the potential to bring benefits. So there is no “Original Sin” in Islam. It is in this connection that Islam strongly rejects the idea of God begetting a son to redeem the world from the Original Sin. For Islam believes that God is one only; He does not beget, nor is He begotten; and there is no one like God. Hence, sin, from the point of Islam, is a conscious and wilful act that violates a commandment of God or the right of a fellow being. We cannot consider a person to be a sinner if he or she acts under duress or out of ignorance. For human accountability is an important aspect of justice as envisaged in Islam. No one can be truly held accountable for an action that he has no power to avoid. It is that when a human being contradicts God’s commandments or His will, he commits sins. Islam teaches that sin is an avoidable act that harms the perpetrator’s own soul. This means that there is no innate or inherited nature that prompts a person to disobey God. That is to say, it is a person’s free choice whether to sin or not; and one’s disposition to sin is only as much as, if not less than, their inclination to do well. Islam teaches that a person’s motive should be taken into consideration when we judge his or her actions. We know that motive is something that is in the mind of the people and even if they speak out why they have acted in a particular

way, we have no means of verifying their claim. Adam committed such a sin, which led to his expulsion from the Garden of Eden. But Adam repented and prayed to God for forgiveness, which God granted him, as mentioned in Surah (Chapter) 2, verse (ayat) 35-37: “Then learnt Adam from his Lord words of inspiration, and his Lord turned towards him; for He is Oft-returning, Most Merciful”. This means that unlike Christianity, which teaches that all the children of Adam are sinful because of Adam’s sin, Islam teaches that all humans are innocent by birth and they become sinful only when they consciously commit a sin. Islam regards the concept of “original sin” and the need for atonement by God Himself – via dying on the Cross- as a pure invention of Christians. Adam and Eve lived and walked with God while in the Garden of Eden. When they disobeyed the commandment of God, they were denied access to the Garden and a personal relationship with God. The act of defiance by Adam and Eve changed humans’ perception of reality. They now understood that they could act on their own and do exactly what they wanted. The act of disobedience caused an irrevocable change in the outlook of humans. It has nothing to do with punishing future children but the changing of reality.

Islam recognises five degrees of sin, in order of severity:

1. *Sayyia, khatia*: mistakes (Quran 7:168, 17:31, 40:45, 47:19, 48:2)
2. *Itada, junah, dhanb*: immorality (Quran 2:190, 17:17, 33:55)
3. *Haram*: transgressions (Quran 5:4, 6:146)
4. *Ithm, dhulam, fujur, su, sasad, fisk, kufr*: wickedness and depravity (Quran 2:99, 205, 4:50, 12:79, 38:62, 82:14)
5. *Shirk*: ascribing a partner to God (Quran 4:48)

There is considerable difference among scholars as to which sins are Al-Kaba’r (major sins). According to Sahih Bukhari there are seven Al-Kaba’r (major sins) according to this tradition.²

“Avoid the seven noxious things” – and after having said this, the prophet (saw) mentioned them: “associating anything with Allah; magic (Equivalent to Witchcraft and Sorcery); killing one whom Allah has declared inviolate without just cause, consuming the property of an orphan, devouring usury, turning back when the army advances, and

slandering chaste women who are believers but indiscreet."Abdullah ibn Abbas said: "Seventy is closer to their number than seven"³

It is believed that *Iblis* (Satan) has a significant role in tempting humankind towards sin. Thus, Islamic theology identifies and warns of an external enemy of humankind who leads humankind towards sin (Quran 7:27, 4:199, 3:55, 2:30, 7:11, 20:116). Muslims believe that Allah is angered by sin and punishes some sinners with the fires of *jahannam* (hell), but that He is also *ar-rahman* (the Merciful) and *al-ghaffar* (the Oft-Forgiving). It is believed that the *jahannam* fire has purification functionality and that after purification, an individual who has been condemned to enter *jahannam* is eligible to go to *jannah* (the Garden), if he "had an atom's worth of faith" Some Quranic commentaries such as Allameh Tabatabaei state that the fire is nothing but a transformed form of the human's sin itself:

"Those who unjustly eat up the property of orphans, eat up a Fire into their own bodies: They will soon be enduring a Blazing Fire!" (Quran 4:10).

"Those who conceal Allah's revelations in the Book (The Bible), and purchase for them a miserable profit – they swallow into themselves naught but Fire!" (Quran 2:174).

While discussing the concept of sin in Islam it has to be noted that one man's sin cannot be transferred to another; nor can the reward due to a person be transferred either. Every individual is responsible only for his or her actions, for God is never unjust. This is made clear in Quran, Chapter 17:25: "Who receives guidance, receives it for his own benefit: who goes astray does so to his own loss. No bearer of burdens can bear the burden of another: nor would We (God) punish until We had sent a messenger to give warning". Every individual is an independent person who is responsible for his or her actions alone. There is no need for salvation from sin, for there is no original burden. One's success in the Hereafter lies in his living a righteous life in this world.

Islamic conceptions of atonement for sin

Quran teaches that the main way back to Allah is through genuine *tawbah* (repentance) which literally means 'to return'. While legally it signifies turning to God for forgiveness of a sin or an act of

disobedience, its primary sense of turning to God as a personal act of love and devotion, and not necessarily from a state of sin, is a more exalted and deeper level of repentance. The Prophet Muhammad, for example, whom Muslims believe to have been protected from all sin by God, is said to have declared 'I turn to God every day seventy times'. Repentance is more than just asking for forgiveness, it is a turning to God with sincere love and devotion. The change of heart, as the Quran makes clear, can itself only be achieved by divine grace. Two other Arabic words used for repentance emphasize this wider meaning. *Awbah* has the sense of repeated returning to God with humility, devotion and praise and *inabah* signifies turning to God for help in total submission to his will.

The Quran has more than ninety words for sin or offences against God or fellow human beings. Yet, there is no doctrine of original sin as we have discussed earlier, although the human propensity to do evil is clearly recognised. As a just and moral sovereign, God is severe in punishment, but more important his mercy is repeatedly affirmed. "God is Oft-Forgiving and Most-Merciful" (5:98). To despair of God's infinite mercy is itself a grave sin. God says in the Quran, "O my servants, who have transgressed against their souls, despair not of the Mercy of Allah, for Allah forgives all sins" (39:53). God's mercy is affirmed in the *Hadith* or traditions. It is said that, "When God created the creation, He prescribed with His own hand for Himself, "my mercy shall overcome my wrath".

One of the traditional stories in Islam speaks of God seeking the sinner and rejoicing at his repentance. On one occasion Muhammad, according to one of the Companions, Anas, said, Allah says: "When a servant of Mine advances to me by a foot, I advance to him by a yard and when he advances to me a yard, I advance towards him the length of his arms' spread. When he comes to me walking, I go to him running".⁴

Repentance or turning to God is prominent in the Sufi tradition. For the famous Persian Sufi master Hujwiri (1077), it is the first station of the traveller on the way to truth. For Sufi, the mystical life is a journey from God to the world of created things and back to God the creator of all things. This journey consists of acts of worship and obedience and a turning from carnal and worldly temptations. There is an ascetic strain in Sufism but also a deep sense of the love and mercy of God. Repentance

is the means by which one is turned towards God.⁵ As Shaykh Ibrahim al-Daqqaq (1015-1021) said, “Repentance means that you should be to God a face without a back even as you have formerly been unto him a back without a face”.⁶

The Shi’ite tradition with its more pessimistic view of human life sees sin as a primary cause of life’s troubles. Repentance, as Mahmoud Ayoub says, has therefore a redemptive significance and can help to lessen the evils in the world. Repentance should be expressed publicly through penitential liturgies.⁷

The following texts explicate the concept of repentance vividly.

“Say: O my Servants who have transgressed against their souls! Despair not of the Mercy of Allah: for Allah forgives all sins: for He is Oft-Forgiving, Most Merciful. Turn ye to our Lord in repentance and bow to His will, before the Penalty comes on you: after that ye shall not be helped (Quran 39:53).”

“Verily, Allah accepts the repentance of those who do evil in ignorance and repent soon afterwards, to them Allah will turn in Mercy, for Allah is Full of Knowledge and Wisdom. And of no effect is the repentance of those who continue to do evil until death faces one of them and he says “now have I repented indeed”, nor of those who die rejecting faith: for them have we prepared a chastisement most grievous (Quran 4:17).”

‘Islam’ in Arabic represents two basic concepts: One is ‘submission’ and the other is ‘peace’. As the name of the religion, it stands for ‘the peace we can attain in this world and the next by submitting to the One and Only God of the universe’. Except two chapters the rest of the 112 Chapters of Quran begin with a verse: *Bimillah hir Rahman nir Rahim* (God is most compassionate and most merciful). God is ready to forgive the sins if one repents. Hence, Islam does not accept any blood sacrifice for sin. The Islamic understanding of forgiveness is that it is made on the basis of divine grace and repentance. According to Islam, no sacrifice can add to divine grace nor replace the necessity of repentance. In the Islamic theology, the animal sacrifice or blood are not directly linked to atonement (Quran 22:37). On the other hand, the sacrifice is done to help the poor, and in remembrance of Abraham’s willingness to sacrifice his son at God’s command. In many verses of Quran, Allah promises to forgive the sins of his creatures (Quran 47:2, 29:7, 14:23, 11:114).

The Islamic Personal Law (Sharia) specifies the atonement for particular sins. Depending on the sin, the atonement can range from repentance and compensation for sin if possible, feeding the poor, freeing slaves to even stoning to death or cutting hands.⁸

Sin and Forgiveness in Islam

Islam speaks about two aspects of forgiveness:

1. Allah's Forgiveness;
2. Human Forgiveness.

1. Allah's Forgiveness:

It is said that Allah *subhanahu wa ta'ala* is the most forgiving. There are many names of Allah given in the Quran. Some of these names are related to His mercy and forgiveness. Let us analyse the theological significance of these names to verify the concept of forgiveness in Islam:

1.1. Al-Ghafoor (The most forgiving):

This name occurs in the Quran more than seventy times. There are other names from the same root, such as *Ghafir* and *Ghaffar*. The meaning of the "*ghafara*" is to cover, to hide and from it comes the meaning "to excuse", "to pardon", "to remit" and "to forgive". Allah does all these things. In the Quran, it is mentioned that Allah does not forgive the Shirk (without repentance) but He may forgive every other sin for whomsoever He wills (al-Nisa 4:116).

1.2. Al-'Afuw:

This brings out another dimension of forgiveness. This name occurs in the Quran five times. Literally the word 'Afuw' means "to release" "to heal", "to restore", and "to remit". Thus, in relation to Allah it means "to release us from the burden of punishment due to our sins and mistakes" and subsequently, "to restore our honour after we have dishonoured ourselves by committing sins and making mistakes." Sometimes in the Quran both names: 'Afuw and Ghafoor come together.

1.3. Al-Tawwab:

The literal meaning of the word is 'the acceptor of repentance'. This name of Allah is mentioned in the Quran about 11 times. Allah accepts

the repentance of those who sincerely repent and turn to him. The word “*tawwab*” gives the sense of “oft-returning” which means that Allah again and again accepts repentance. We commit sins and mistakes then we repent, He accepts our repentance. Then again we commit sins and make mistakes and when we repent, He again very kindly accepts us and gives us another chance.

1.4. Al-Haleem (The Clement):

This name is mentioned fifteen times in the Quran. This means that Allah is not quick to judgement. He gives time. He patiently waits for his servants to return to Him.

1.5. Al-Rahman and al-Rahim (The most Merciful and most Compassionate):

These names are the most frequent in the Quran. Al-Rahman is mentioned 57 times and al-Rahim is mentioned 115 times. Al-Rahman indicates that Allah’s mercy is abundant and plenty and al-Rahim indicates that this is always the case with Allah. He is full of love and mercy and He is ever Merciful.

The Quran teaches that Allah is a Judge and He also punishes, but Allah is not bound to punish. The justice of Allah, according to Quran, is that Allah does not and will not inflict undue punishment on any person. He will not ignore the good of any person. But if He wishes to forgive any sinner, He has full freedom to do that. His mercy is unlimited and His love is infinite.

B. Human Forgiveness:

Just as it is important to believe in the mercy and forgiveness of Allah, it is also necessary to base human relations on forgiveness. As in Christianity forgiving each other, even forgiving one’s enemies is one of the most important of Islamic teachings. In the Quran Allah has described the Believers as “those who avoid major sins and acts of indecencies and when they are angry they forgive.” (al-Sura 42:37). Later in the same Surah Allah says, “The reward of the evil is the evil thereof, but whosoever forgives and makes amends, his reward is upon Allah.” (al-Sura 42:40). In another place the Quran says, “If you punish, then punish with the like of that wherewith you were afflicted. But if you

endure patiently, indeed it is better for you. Endure patiently. Your patience is not except through the help of Allah (al-Nahl, 16:126-127).

In one Hadith (Prophet's sayings) the Prophet said that Allah has commanded him about nine things. One of them he mentioned was "that I forgive those who do wrong to me".

The Prophet Muhammad was the most forgiving person. He was ever ready to forgive his enemies. When he went to Ta'if to preach the message of Allah, its people ill-treated him. They ridiculed him and hit him with stones.

He left the city humiliated and wounded. When he took shelter under a tree, the angel of Allah visited him and told him that Allah sent him to destroy the people of Ta'if because of their sin of mistreating their Prophet. The Prophet prayed to Allah to save the people of Ta'if, because what they did was out of their ignorance. He said, "Oh Allah, guide these people, because they did not know what they were doing." When he entered the city of Mecca after the victory, the Prophet had in front of him some of his staunchest enemies. Those who fought him for many years persecuted his followers and killed many of them. Now he had full power to do whatever he wanted to punish them for their crimes. It is reported that the Prophet asked them, "What do you think I shall do to you now?" They pleaded for mercy. The Prophet said, "Today I shall say to you what Joseph (referring to Prophet Yusuf as mentioned in the Quran, Yusuf 12:92) said to his brothers, "No blame on you today. Go, you are all free." Soon they all came and accepted Islam. He forgave even Hind who had caused the murder of his uncle Hamza. After killing his body he mutilated and chewed his liver. When she accepted Islam, the Prophet even forgave her.⁹

A very striking example of forgiveness we find in the Quran is in reference to the most unfortunate event of "Slander of Sayyidah Aisha" (wife of Muhammad). A few hypocrites of Madina accused her of her noble character. One of the slanderers turned out to be Mistah, the cousin of Aisha's father Abu Bakr. Abu Bakr used to give financial help to this young man. After he slandered his daughter, Abu Bakr vowed not to help him anymore. But Allah reminded Abu Bakr and through him all the Believers, "Let not those among you who are endowed with grace and amplitude of means resolve by oath against helping their kinsmen, those

in want and those who migrated in the path of Allah. Let them forgive you? Indeed Allah is oft-Forgiving, most Merciful.” (Al-Nur 24:22) Abu Bakr came out of his home and said, “Yes, indeed, I want Allah’s forgiveness. He not only continued to help him but he gave him more. Islam emphasizes mercy, kindness and love. Justice, law and order are necessary for the maintenance of a social order, but there is also a need for forgiveness to heal the wounds and to restore good relations between the people.¹⁰

Since God is Almighty, He does not need the charade concocted by other religious traditions in order to forgive our sins. In the Quran, God says we are all created in a state of goodness (30:30); He has not burdened us with any “original sin”, having forgiven Adam and Eve ((2:36-38; 7:23, 24) as He forgives us (11:90; 39:53-56). As we are all personally responsible for our actions (2:286); 6:164) there is no need for a humanly concocted saviour in Islam; salvation comes from God alone (28:67).

Thus Islam seeks to restore true meaning to monotheism, for in the Quran God asks: “Who can be better in religion than one who submits his whole self to God, does good, and follows the way of Abraham the true in faith?” (4:125); 41:33).

Although, as we have seen, there is much in Islam about God’s mercy, there is also clear teaching about a day of Judgement, when each person’s deeds will be weighed on an exact balance (7; 8:21, 47:23, 103f; 101:6-9) and the book of the record for each person will be opened (10; 61; 17; 13f). No one can help another person; each person is responsible for his own actions. Yet the possibility of intercession especially by Muhammad and later by angels and martyrs came to be accepted, and this modified such strict accounting.¹¹ One of the early Sufis, Rabi’s of Basra (717-801) recognised that the vision of God was reward enough. “O my Lord”, she wrote, “if I worship you from fear of hell, burn me in hell; and if I worship you from Hope of Paradise, exclude me thence; but if I worship you for Thine own sake, then withhold not from me Thine Eternal Beauty.”¹²

As for the wicked, the Quran says that they will burn ‘as long as heaven and earth endure’ (11, 106-7). There are two conditions attached to this. One is ‘except as Allah wills’ and the other, in the view of some

theologians, is that punishments are not eternal because the heavens and the earth as we see them are not eternal. Another verse says, 'Those who deny Our revelations, we will roast in a fire. As often as their skins are consumed we will give them fresh skins, so that they may taste the torment' (4, 56).

Both Christianity and Islam try to balance belief in both the justice and mercy of God. God's justice is important, although it is not perhaps given adequate attention in modern Christian circles. The justice of God emphasises our moral responsibility for our behaviour matters. It also suggests that there is redress in another world to the injustices and suffering of this world. Yet too easily pictures of God's punishment of sinners can give a picture of a God of vengeance, which is especially dangerous when humans take it upon themselves to be agents of that vengeance. Umar ibn Khattab told of the occasion when some prisoners of war were brought to the Prophet. Among them was a woman who ran all over the place looking for her child. When she lifted it close towards her and suckled it. The Prophet then asked, "Can you imagine this woman throwing her child into the fire?" When his companions said, "No", Muhammad said, "God is much more compassionate towards his servants that she is towards her child."¹³

The Quran suggests that those who appear before God after death are involved in deciding their own guilt or innocence. God will say to every person:

'Read your own record:
Sufficient is thy soul
This day to make out
An account against thee' (17,14).

According to one of the Islamic commentaries, "our true accusers are our own deeds".¹⁴ The distinguished scholar Huston Smith explains, "What death burns away is self-serving defences, forcing one to see with total objectivity how one has lived one's life. In the uncompromising light of that vision, where no dark and hidden corners are allowed, it is one's own actions that rise up to accuse or confirm".¹⁵ In St. John's Gospel Jesus says that he did not come to condemn the world. People condemn themselves by not coming to the light for fear that their deeds will be exposed (Jn. 3, 17-20 and 12, 47-8).

Sadly, the application of justice in some Islamic states does not reflect the compassion of God. As Farid Esack says, "The idea of an Allah who is compassionate and merciful is one that we need to retrieve in order to recapture Islam from those who insist that our faith and Allah are only about anger and vengeance".¹⁶

Most offences against another human being are also offences against God. This means that repentance addressed to God is necessary as well as compensation to the injured party. It is a debated question in Islam whether, when compensation has been made and repentance is genuine, punishment is still required. Maybe acceptance of punishment is a sign of contradiction. It is interesting to compare stories of how Muhammad and Jesus dealt with a woman who had committed adultery. It is said that woman who had committed this offence confessed to the Prophet and asked that she be duly punished, which meant being stoned. The woman was pregnant. The Prophet told her to go away and wait until the baby was born. In due course, she returned with the child in her arms and again asked for punishment. The Prophet sent her away again to nurse the child until it was weaned. The mother returned again leading her child who had a piece of bread in his mouth. Had the woman not returned and simply repented, she would have escaped punishment. But since she wished her sin to be expiated, the Prophet ordered that she be stoned to death. Afterwards he prayed over her and gave her an honourable burial. Umar B.al-Khattab, who was to become the second Caliph, protested that Muhammad had prayed over a woman who had committed adultery. Muhammad replied, "But she had performed such a sincere act of repentance which, if it were divided among seventy inhabitants of Madina, it would suffice for them. Is there anything nobler than her offering her life freely to God?"

In this connection it is important to recognise that cruel punishments such as stoning for adultery or amputation of a hand for theft, which are unacceptable to many cultures, are equally unacceptable to many Muslims. It is also helpful to remember that the Arab society in which Muhammad came to have political power was one of tribal rivalries. As Muhammad Siddiqi¹⁷ makes clear the bonds of blood and kin-relationship were transformed into a faith-based unity with a single worship and command. The Quran sought to approve of private retaliation. Although it is still allowed, it insisted that revenge, if exacted,

must be strictly limited, and made clear that forgiveness or compounding for money were preferable (Quran 2, 178-9).

Legal systems based on the Quran tend to give greater weight to the injured party. Religious teaching focuses on the inner relation of the soul to God, which is known only to God. Legal systems have to focus on outward behaviour. Neglect of prayers out of laziness and apostasy are offences, but the law has to be satisfied by an outward show of repentance. God's verdict has to be left till the Day of Judgement. If punishment is carried out here on earth, the intention is to bring the recalcitrant person back to the community or to make him an example to others.¹⁸

Where injury is caused to another person, the first requirement of the wrongdoer is that he should compensate the victim. The prophet, however, urged victims to offer forgiveness:

Let them forgive and overlook,
Do you not wish
That Allah should forgive you? (Hadith 24)

According to an early tradition, Muhammad advised, "If anyone would like God to save him from the anxieties of Day of Resurrection, he should grant a respite to one who is in straitened circumstances or remit his debt" (Mishkat 12,9) Aisha (Wife of Prophet Muhammad) reported that the Prophet said, 'Avert the infliction of prescribed penalties on Muslims as much as you can, and let a man go if there is any way out, for it is better for a leader to make a mistake in forgiving than to make a mistake in punishing' (Mishkat 16,1).

Hence, in the Quran the emphasis is on the positive content of forgiveness and salvation. It is not conceived as a negation of pain and liberation from evil. It consists in the sense of fulfilment, the feeling of realization and the thrill of expansion. Human being is endowed with a number of potentialities. By developing these one reaches one's full stature and qualifies for still higher stages waiting him. One must discover in what direction his self can develop and then he must create the conditions, physical as well as social, which favour the development. God forgives the sinner and causes his self to grow (Quran 91:9-10).

Violence a Gravest sin!

Islam, as expounded in the classical books of theology and law, does not bear a message of violence or terrorism. In fact, *salaam* (peace and tranquillity) is a central tenet of Islamic belief. The absence of peace is identified in the Quran as a largely negative condition; it is variously described as a trial and tribulation, as a curse or punishment, or sometimes, as a necessary evil. The Quran asserts that if it had not been for divine benevolence, many mosques, churches, synagogues, and homes would have been destroyed because of the ignorance and pettiness of human beings (Quran 22:40).

The Islamic historical experience was primarily concerned not with war-making or terrorism but with civilization-building. Islamic theology instructs that an integral part of the divine covenant given to human beings is to occupy them with building and creating, not destroying life. The Quran teaches that the act of destroying or spreading ruin on this earth is one of the gravest of sins possible. *Fasd fi al-ard*, which means to corrupt the earth by destroying the beauty of creation, is considered an ultimate act of blasphemy against God (Quran 2:27, 5:32, 13:25). Those who corrupt the earth by destroying the earth, by destroying lives, property and nature are designated as *mufsidun* who, in effect, wage war against God by dismantling the very fabric of existence (2:27, 13:25). In addition, the Quran states that God has made people different and diverse, and that they will remain so until the final day. Accordingly, human diversity is part of the divine plan, and the challenge is for human beings to co-exist and interact despite their differences (Quran 11:118). The Quran proclaims it in an unequivocal fashion: "God has made you into many nations and tribes so that you will come to know one another. Those most honoured in the eyes of God are those who are most pious" (Quran 49:13). From this, classical Muslim scholars reached the reasonable conclusion that terrorism is not the means most conducive to getting "to know one another." Thus, they argued that the exchange of technology and merchandise is, in most cases, a superior course of action to warfare. In the opinion of most classical jurists, war, unless it is purely defensive, is not to be preferred, and must be treated as a last resort because war and terrorism are not superior moral virtues.¹⁹

Despite this rich doctrinal and historical background, the dilemmas of a modern Muslim intellectual persist. Many classical Muslim

scholars, for instance, insisted on a conception of the world that is bifurcated and dichotomous. Those scholars argued that the world is divided into the abode of Islam (*dar al-Islam*) and abode of war (*dar al-harb*); the two can stop fighting for a while, but one must inevitably prevail over the other. According to these scholars, Muslims must give non-Muslims one of three options; either become a Muslim, pay a poll tax, or fight. These classical scholars were willing to tolerate differences as long as the existence of these differences did not challenge Muslim political supremacy and dominance. On the other hand, many classical scholars argued that instead of a two-part division of the world, one ought to recognise a third category, and that is the abode of non-belligerence or neutrality (*dar al-sulh* or *'ahd*) - an abode that is not Muslim, but that has a peaceful relationship with the Muslim world.²⁰

But the fact that the Islamic scholastic tradition is not unitary, and that it is often diverse and multi-faceted is hardly surprising. What is surprising and often aggravating is the extent to which Islamic debates in the modern age have become politicized and polarized. The real challenge that confronts Islam is that political interests have come to dominate the public discourse, and to a large extent, moral discourses have become marginalized in modern Islam. In many ways, since the onslaught of colonialism and its aftermath, Muslims have become largely pre-occupied with the attempt to remedy a collective feeling of powerlessness and frustrating sense of political defeat, often by engaging in highly sensationalistic acts of power symbolism. The normative imperatives and intellectual subtleties of the Islamic moral tradition are not treated with the analytic and critical rigour that this tradition rightly deserves, but are rendered subservient to political expedience and symbolic displays of power. The events of September 11 grew out of the historic tensions between the civilizations we speak of as "Islam" and "the West".

This is what I like to call this contemporary doctrinal dynamic as the predominance of the theology of power in modern Islam, and it is this theology that is a direct contributor to the emergence of highly radicalised Islamic groups, such as the Islamic Jihad or al-Qa'ida.²¹ Far from being authentic expressions of inherited Islamic paradigms, or a natural out-growth of the classical tradition, these are thoroughly a

by-product of colonialism and modernity. Such groups ignore the history of the Islamic civilization, with all its richness and diversity, and reduce Islam to a single dynamic - the dynamic of power. They tend to define Islam as an ideology of nationalistic defiance to the other—a vulgar form of obstructionism to the hegemony of the Western world. Usama bin Laden and others are radicals frustrated by the failure of existing governments to deliver on promises of economic and political development. Driven to despair by the failure of the international community to protect Muslims in Chechnya and Palestine, they find in Islam a convenient vocabulary for the articulation of grievances and the justification of acts of defiance.¹ In this regard Member of Parliament Mehmood Madani, who heads the India's largest party of clerics, the Jamiat Ullema-e-Islam openly expressed in his interview in Times of India on April 22, 2008: *'the terrorists are besmirching the name of Islam for attaining unaccountable power. It is a sinful act. These terrorists are not promoting either popular welfare or democratic rights of the people. But they constitute a threat that has to be met. Islamic terrorism is primarily a threat to Muslims and the need of the hour is to take action to get rid of this sin.'* Therefore, Islam, being a moral vision given to humanity, is constructed into the antithesis of the West. In essence what prevails is an aggravated siege mentality that suspends the moral principles of the religion in pursuit of political power. In fact, the Quran goes on to specify that if the enemy ceases hostilities and seeks peace, Muslims should seek peace as well. Failure to seek peace without a just cause is considered arrogant and sinful (Quran 4:90).

Conclusion

Islam, one of the major religions commanding the devotion of second largest community of the world's population, is actually a way of life. It is a living tradition engaging and in turn engaged by successive generations of believers. Motivated by the Quran and the example of the Prophet as depictions of that which is good, beautiful and true in human experience, such believers seek to increase the range of order and meaning in the world. It gives detailed rules on marriage, divorce and inheritance, etiquette of business transactions, punishment for crimes, and rules and norms of war. Islam not only moulds the beliefs but also moulds the daily behaviour and activities in the life of the

people. God has a plan for everyone and he guides us accordingly (Quran 17:25). In this context, in Islam, a sin is an act against the will of God. Every individual is responsible only for his or her actions. The effect of one's sin cannot be transferred to another. Human beings are innocent by birth and they consciously commit a sin and so sinfulness is never a state of being. Allah has left the door always open for repentance of one's sin. He has also committed Himself to turn with forgiveness to anyone who genuinely turns to Him in repentance.

Prophet Muhammad and those who followed him saw the world as a heedless place in which human beings ignored their duty to God. From the start, Muslims were at war with this milieu. Called to live as idol breakers, they carved out a political and geographic space in which human beings could live as "submitters" (Muslims) obedient to the will of God. They believed that it was their destiny to enlarge this space so as to make the entire world conform to the divine will. For much of the first millennium of Islamic history the progress of Islamic culture and the success of Islamic armies seemed to confirm this destiny. Like all believers, they are capable of the complete range of behaviours characteristic of human beings: love and hate, joy and sorrow, justice and injustice, creativity and destruction. How shall we speak of sin in Islam after September 11, 2002? As a religion practised by millions of human beings. No more, and no less!

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This view is powerfully elaborated by John Esposito in his, *Unholy War: Terror in the Name of Isla*, (London: Oxford University Press, 2002), p. 220.